

*CLEAN
AND
GREEN*

Dr Martina Fantini, CLEANKER,
discusses the reduction of CO₂
emissions in the cement industry.

The cement industry is a key sector for the reduction of CO₂ emissions. CO₂ generation in cement production processes, in fact, cannot be disregarded due to the calcination of limestone; around 60% of the direct CO₂ emissions from the clinker burning process are due to this reaction. In addition, there are emissions from the predominant combustion of fossil fuels, as well as from the generation of electric power required by the process as indirect CO₂ emissions. Cement production is thus responsible for about 27% of global anthropogenic CO₂ emissions from industrial sources worldwide, and for 6 to 7% of global anthropogenic CO₂ emissions. According to International Energy Agency (IEA) and ZEP studies, the cement industry should contribute to the largest CO₂ emission reduction through carbon capture and storage (CCS) in Europe, in order to meet the target of 2°C of global temperature increase (the IEA 2DS scenario).

There are currently no feasible methods to produce clinker, and thus cement, without releasing CO₂ from the calcination of CaCO₃. Given the

lifetime of a cement plant (30 – 50 years), the carbon capture technologies to be developed

Figure 1. CLEANKER consortium.

Figure 2. 3D model of the CLEANKER demonstrator.

have to be retrofittable. In addition to oxyfuel combustion and post-combustion solvent-based capture technologies, which have attracted most of the research efforts up to now, calcium looping is recognised as a promising emerging technology for CO₂ capture in cement plants. Calcium looping (or carbonate looping) is a regenerative process that takes advantage of the capacity of calcium oxide-based sorbents to capture CO₂ at high temperatures. The process is divided into two basic steps:

1. The capture of CO₂ through the carbonation of CaO to form CaCO₃ in a reactor operating around 650°C.
2. Oxyfuel calcination in a reactor operating above 900°C – 920°C, which makes the CaO available again and releases a gas stream of nearly pure CO₂.

The highly integrated calcium looping process configuration enables CO₂ capture with an efficiency target over 90% and high energy efficiency. The overall energy consumption can be kept low by proper integration with raw meal preheating and heat recovery from the kiln flue gases. The adoption of entrained flow gas-solid reactors is particularly suitable for this calcium looping configuration because, in such reactors, the same very fine raw material can be used for clinker production (CaO) and for CO₂ sorption, without additional milling requirements. Moreover, entrained flow reactors are already commonly used in cement plants.

The core activity of the CLEANKER project is the design, construction, and operation of a CaL demonstration system, including the entrained-flow carbonator (the CO₂ absorber) and the entrained-flow oxyfuel calciner (the sorbent regenerator). This demonstration system, connected to the Buzzi Unicem kiln of the Vernasca cement plant in Italy, will capture the CO₂ from a portion of the flue gases of the kiln, using as CO₂ sorbent the same raw meal that is used for clinker production. Other activities carried out by the consortium (Figure 1) will include: the screening of different raw meals to assess their properties as CO₂ sorbent; reactors and process modelling; a scale-up study; economic analysis; a life cycle assessment (LCA); a CO₂ transport, storage, and utilisation study; demonstration of the complete value chain, including mineral carbonation of waste ash with the CO₂ captured in the pilot system; and an exploitation study for the demonstration of the technology.

The CLEANKER implementation plan spans four years from October 2017 to September 2021. The first year has been devoted to the detailed design of the CaL demonstration system and characterisation of raw meals; the second year is

focused on the construction of the demonstrator; and the last two years are dedicated to experimental campaigns, results analysis, evaluation of technology scale-up, economic analysis, and an LCA of the integrated system.

The first 1.5 year main results are related to raw meal characterisation, modelling, engineering, and CO₂ mineral carbonation experiments with waste materials, methodology for carbon capture utilisation and storage (CCUS) scenarios modelling, and CCS regulations.

Raw meal characterisation

Characterisation of raw meal was necessary to assess the behaviour of the sorbent in the future configuration. The Vernasca raw meal was characterised based on a developed text matrix at the University of Stuttgart test rig, in order to quantify the kinetics rates of calcination and carbonation. The Vernasca raw meal is a mixture of a high purity limestone and marl. Compared to natural limestones, the calcined raw meal presented a complex behaviour as sorbent. This is mainly due to the formation of belite (Ca₂SiO₄), which reduces the amount of CaO available to react with CO₂. Thus, the formation of belite through the reaction of SiO₂ with CaCO₃ and CaO has been studied by means of thermogravimetric analysis, and simplified models have been tuned to the experimental results to obtain kinetic parameters. The decay constants obtained are shown to be comparable to typical values reported for other standard limestones, but the raw meal has yielded much more complex behaviour with the operating conditions due to belite formation.

Engineering

To support the design of the demonstration plant, heat and mass balances have been carried out. Nine different cases have been calculated, combining the following features:

- ▶ Different raw meal/kiln gas flow rate ratio.
- ▶ Different CaO sorbent capacity.
- ▶ Different solids circulation rate between the CaL reactors.
- ▶ An oxygen-blown and air-blown calciner.
- ▶ Oxyfuel calciner operation and a deactivated carbonator.
- ▶ High purity limestone feed rather than raw meal.
- ▶ Calciner exhaust quenching by extra raw meal feeding.

The variety of cases presented covers a wide spectrum of possible plant operating conditions. Based on the heat and mass balances calculated, the layout of the calcium looping demonstration plant to be built in Vernasca was

defined. Interconnections to the existing plant, quantification of additional loads to be considered in the existing structures, identification of all measuring devices and drive motors, and definition of all individual machinery and pieces of equipment have been defined together with the definition of measurement points and instrumentation. A 3D model layout of the demonstration plant is shown in Figure 2.

The carbonator (the long red pipe shown in Figure 2) is a key component for the calcium looping system. The size of the pilot plant is determined by the flow rate of the gases sent to the carbonator, which is about 1000 Nm³/hour, leading to a gas superficial velocity of around 15 m/sec. along the carbonator with a 250 mm inner dia. The amount of raw meal fed to the demonstrator is defined by keeping the same ratio between the flow rates of raw meal and rotary kiln off-gas of industrial cement kilns. The carbonator is an adiabatic reactor with removable insulation, working with an inlet adiabatic mixing temperature of 600°C that results from mixing between the gas, the solids from the calciner, and the recirculated solids. Because of the carbonation reaction, temperature increases along the carbonator. This temperature increase is somewhat mitigated by heat losses and by air in-leakages. The carbonator has a gooseneck shape with a 250 mm dia. in the up-flow section and an increased 350 mm dia. in the down-stream section, which allows the residence time in the reactor to increase.

A complete safety and risk analysis, as per the directive 2006/42/EC, for the demonstrator plant and its machinery was carried out by Buzzi Unicem. Buzzi Unicem also took care of getting in touch with the local authorities to achieve the official permits to construct the new plant.

CO₂ mineral carbonation

Once the demonstrator is constructed, within the experimental campaigns, mineralisation tests will be carried out. To prepare the ground for these experimental activities, different waste materials including burnt oil shale, concrete demolition wastes, cement bypass dust, and blastfurnace slag sampled from Estonian, Italian, and German power plants, and a Buzzi cement plant in Italy, were tested via the wet direct carbonation method. The CO₂ uptake was mainly attributed by the free lime content, which is relatively high (10 – 37%) in burnt oil shale and cement bypass dust samples, but which is not available in concrete demolition wastes and blastfurnace slag. Selected types of burnt oil shale and cement bypass dust could be used as effective sorbents in the proposed CO₂ mineralisation process, binding up to 0.18 kg of CO₂ per kilogram of waste. A kinetic model was built to

predict process parameters at given operating conditions.

CCS regulation

To complete the framework, international and national regulations related to CCUS technology and their national implementations have been studied in detail and compared for the five countries (Italy, Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania, and Russia) involved in the planned CCUS scenarios of the CLEANKER project. National greenhouse gas and CO₂ fossil emissions have been compared with the 1990 year and their climate and energy strategic targets have been discussed. Two of the main conclusions up to now are:

- ▶ The climate strategic targets should be increased in all the studied countries to reach the Paris Agreement targets, and CCUS technology should be included in the list of technological priorities together with renewables and other options in all the studied countries.
- ▶ Educational and increasing public awareness activities, supported by academic and research institutions and the media, are needed in all countries to explain the benefits of climate change mitigation. ■

Acknowledgements

This project has received funding from the EU's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 764816. This work is supported by the China Government (National Natural Science Foundation of China) under contract No. 91434124 and No. 51376105.

Disclaimer: The European Commission support for the production of this publication does not constitute endorsement of the contents, which reflects the views only of the author, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

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